

www.arseam.com

Impact Factor: 3.43

IMPACT OF DEMONETIZATION ON THE DIFFERENT SECTOR OF ECONOMY

Dr. Sangeeta Malpani

(H.O.D.) Banking,

B.N.P.G. Girls college Rajsamand

Rajasthan, India

Dr. Inder Singh Rathore

(H.O.D.) Sociology

B.N.P.G. Girls college Rajsamand

Rajasthan, India

ABSTRACT

Demonetization was an imitative step which taken by Indian govt. At that time it was so painful and not accepted by a large part of country but slowly and slowly it accepted. Due to demonetization different type of impact shown on different sector of economy. The supply of money increase in banking sector but many sector of economy affected by less working capital and lower availability of cash. Industrial and business sector growth rate decrease at rapid rate. Lower availability of cash in public hand is most powerful factor which decreases the demand of everything capital goods as well as consumer goods but capital goods demand more lower than consumer goods. In this paper we are trying to explore the impact of demonetization on different sector of economy.

Keywords : availability, demonetization, economy, growth, sectors.

Introduction

Demonetization is the act of stripping a currency unit of its status as legal tender. It is the process of ceasing to produce and circulate particular forms of currency. This is necessary whenever there is a change of national currency. The old unit of currency is retired and replaced with a new currency unit. Legal tender is a medium of payment recognized by a legal system to be valid for meeting a financial obligation.

Now we all are really understood the meaning of DEMONETIZATION. It is the processes or an action by which centre govt. and RBI take the decision to cancel the present currency and issue new notes. The cancel currency will be accepted only by banks.

The govt. on 8 Nov. announced that INR1000 and INR 500 note will cease to be legal tender immediately. In recent time Nov. 4, 2016 notes are 17742 bn. (13 %of GDP) the value 500/1000notes circulation 85.5% of notes in circulation Rs. 15342bn (11%of GDP).

As per the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) data, is USD 250 billion (Rs.16.5 trillion) of which 1000 and 500 rupee notes constitute 85 percent (USD 212 billion or Rs. 14.0 trillion). On the assumption that 75 percent of this money is returned to the banking system (either through cash exchange or deposit into accounts), about USD 160 billion or Rs. 10.5 trillion will return to the banking system, while the balance USD 52 billion (Rs. 3.5 trillion) – as much as 2.5 percent of the GDP - will be destroyed. Indent of 535 crore pieces of Rs100 notes, the supply received was only to the tune of 490 crore pieces,” according to the letter. “One cannot understand the reason behind banning the existing Rs500 notes and not providing new supply of Rs500 notes in time,” it added. In the very short-term, delocalization may hurt growth. The squeeze in cash will constrain consumption. Arguably, delocalization will also be disinflationary in as much as it cuts into nondiscretionary consumption of items that go into the Consumer Price Index (CPI) basket

Objectives

- To introduce the term of demonetization
- To explain the impact of demonetization on the different sector of economy.
- To explain the comparative impact of different sectors.

Some reasons of Demonetization

There is usually a solid reason behind the change in currency and countries normally go through a learning curve as the citizens begin to get used to the phasing out of one form of currency and the concurrent introduction of a new form of currency.

Rarely does demonetization take place without some amount of public outcry. However, the indignation of the general public is short lived and soon everyone begins to accept the changes and gradually discontinue use of the older currency. This is particularly true when the government only allows a specific window of time to redeem the discontinued currency for other types of legal tender. Governments across the world have decided to ban currency notes in circulation, rendering huge amounts of cash useless overnight, due to a plethora of reasons. Fight against counterfeiting currencies Stop funding for terror activities Battling black money

Sector	Medium term impact
Financials -Banks	Marginally positive
Financials -NBFCs	Mixed – Divergent across segments
Real estates	Negative
Oil and gas	Neutral
Consumption - staples	Neutral
Consumption - Discretionary	Negative
Infrastructure	Negative
Hospitality	Negative
Autos and auto ancillaries	Negative
Others	Divergent across segments

<u>Sector</u>	<u>Impact</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<p>Banks</p>	Marginally positive	<p>Increased share of saving moving to banks ; high CASA ratio (lower cost of funds)</p> <p>Lower bond yields result in high treasury gains (particular PSU banks)</p> <p>However ,negative from credit growth perspective and asset quality challenges (banks with high SME exposure)</p>
<p>NBFCs</p>	Divergent impact on sub sectors	<p>To long term as borrowers shift to bank accounts <u>Housing finance</u> : negative: LAP/developer loans may see increased delinquencies ; underlying demand slowdown to affect credit growth</p> <p><u>Auto finance</u>: negative:~60-70% transactions are done in cash ; resale values likely to come down for vehicles ; asset quality issue to worsen</p> <p><u>Gold finance</u> : positive in medium term- Near term disbursements to get hit as high cash dealing ;however ,~75% of gold lending is from unorganized segments which will gradually shift to organized players</p> <p><u>Micro finance</u> :positive in medium term --70 % transactions done in cash</p>

		<p>; Near term disbursements / collection to get hit ; however , positive in medium but negative in long term people do not have so much cash so they cannot repay loan and not create any more demand</p>
<p>EPC / Construction</p>	<p>Neutral</p>	<p>Most of these projects have big tickets sizes and revenue is from larger corporate house and governments authorities , which do bank transaction However, for small contractors, due to cash crunch there will be some disruption in medium term. If transaction is possible by bank then impact is neutral. Toll collection , which are mainly done in cash , may see some hiccups in short term</p>
<p>Building material (cement, paint)</p>	<p>Negative</p>	<p>Likely to be negatively impacted as the underlying real estate demand (~60-65% of consumption) will be severely impacted due to curtailment of black money. Lower construction or obstacle in construction and down fall in real state negative impact show in this sector Large part of transactions done in cash in segments like paints ,hence likely to be negatively impacted</p>

<u>Sector</u>	<u>Impact</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<p data-bbox="365 371 517 405" style="text-align: center;">Real estate</p>	<p>Negative</p>	<p data-bbox="935 288 1394 448">Very negative for residential space, land deals. Limited impact on commercial transitions, hospitality or retail.</p> <p data-bbox="935 459 1382 954">Greater impact on small builders and in specific cities / (Tier 2/3 cities, NCR ect.) / Micro markets where cash dealing was more prevalent. Resale properties impacted more than primary sales. Organized builders may also face demand slowdown in near term. Another view is, If supply of resale properties declines due to price crash, it may favorably impact primary sales.</p> <p data-bbox="935 965 1394 1081">Registered prices in residential may go up to adjust for cash component it may face serious fund crunch.</p> <p data-bbox="935 1133 1369 1207">Execution of ongoing project will be affected, and some developers</p> <p data-bbox="935 1258 1394 1626">Positive in long term: Demonetization coupled with real Estate Regulation Act, Bensmi Act, and GST, will transform in real state sector in longer term. Key positives expected increased transparency, improved investor confidence better as to funding, higher FDI likely.</p>

<u>Sector</u>	<u>Impact</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<p>Petroleum and petroleum products</p>	Slightly negative	<p>Temporary pick up in demand due to significant pre – buying of auto fuels</p> <p>Over medium term ,demand , especially for personal transportation could be some what negatively impacted due to high proportion of cash transactions</p>
<p>Citi gas</p>	Neutral	<p>Largely un impacted the demand for CNG might get slightly where cash transactions are high</p>

<u>Sector</u>	<u>Impact</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<p>Hotels</p>	Negative	<p>Demand to be impacted due to slowdown in domestic travel. People avoided the tour, long journey and they do not stay in five star. This time they want to minimize their visiting cost. Near term impact on corporate travel whereas in bound to remain unaffected</p>
<p>Tour operators</p>	Negative	<p><u>Domestic leisure travel</u>: severely impacted as majority of spending is in cash only very urgent, daily job, occasional travel plan prepared during this time.</p> <p><u>Corporate travel</u> : there may be temporary slow down in corporate travel due to cash crunch</p> <p><u>In bound</u>: in bound travel to remain unaffected they have pass for some time long.</p> <p><u>Outbound</u> : outbound travel through unorganized players impacted as foreign exchange usage abroad is mostly in cash</p>

<u>Sector</u>	<u>Impact</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<p data-bbox="231 383 592 416">Autos and auto ancillaries</p>	<p data-bbox="675 719 794 752">Negative</p>	<p data-bbox="836 342 1407 584">Two Wheelers high impact on 2 wheeler sales as large % of rural 2W transitions are in cash, % transitions backed by loans is lower . A few people demanded two wheelers only those who booked before * Nov.</p> <p data-bbox="836 636 1407 752">Passenger Vehicles: Short term impact due to purchase deferment demand will revive in medium term.</p> <p data-bbox="836 804 1407 1046">Luxury cars & SUV: Sales will see significant impact due to wealth deterioration and decline in rural transactions (cash based) No one has dare to to purchase this only for occasional demand is create during these days.</p> <p data-bbox="836 1097 1407 1301">Commercial Vehicles: Negatively impacted. 2nd hand truck sales, which had higher % of cash transactions will decline sharply (both number of transactions and pricing)</p> <p data-bbox="836 1352 1407 1556">Tractors demand to be materially impacted plus questionable trade practices like over invoicing to moderate. Due to decrease in trade and transactions the demand decreases rapidly.</p>

<u>Sector</u>	<u>Impact</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<p>Media – cable TV</p>	<p>Negative</p>	<p>Elongated working capital cycles for multi system operators (MSOs) due to cash dealings of local cable operators (LCOs)</p> <p>APRU growth may be delayed and bad debts may increase due to payments delays by LCOs</p>
<p>Media – print media</p>	<p>Negative</p>	<p>Slow down in real estate (major advertiser in regional print) will impact ad revenue growth for print media down fall in business and personal add create a decline in income</p>
<p>Metals</p>	<p>Negative</p>	<p>Demand slowdown from end consumers such as auto , white goods and constructions is likely to result in lower domestic volumes</p> <p>Pressure on debt serving for leverage metal companies due to drop in volumes</p>

Despite having many positives such as rising tax to GDP, higher GDP growth, lower inflation, higher financial savings, this demonetization move may not curb the root cause of black money. “This initiative addresses the ‘stock’ of black money but not necessarily the flow/fresh creation of black money unless some mechanism is built to track the movement of the new high-value currency notes.

However, such a sudden and drastic step by the government might dissuade some, if not all sections of the society from creating new black money reserves.

Negative Impact of demonetization

Upcoming ordering as well as ongoing activities in roads, water, railways and transmission and distribution sectors, too, will be impacted as payment to labour is usually made in cash. Low number of bank accounts in remote, small villages and supply-chain disruptions could affect demand for consumer staples for a brief while, believe analysts. The demand impact of large-ticket consumer durables items such as apparels, white goods, apparel and the likes could also head south.

Purchase of fertilizers and agrochemicals; usually done via cash, too, could come down. All metal companies will be negatively impacted as a large part of trading in steel and other metals is carried on a cash basis currently.

The short-term debt servicing capacity of small borrowers could be reduced, which may impact the asset quality as well as credit growth of microfinance companies such as Bharat Financial Inclusion, Ujjivan Financial Services, Equitas, etc.

Housing finance companies, too, could witness pressure on their credit quality as well as growth, as fall in real estate prices would impact the loan against property (LAP) business. Even e-commerce players are likely to feel the heat in the near- to medium-term. Cash on delivery forms anywhere between 70 and 90 per cent of e-commerce players' revenues and, hence, can impact valuations of retail e-commerce players

Impacts:

1. Increase the problems of public
2. Down fall in market
3. Decrease the goodwill in international market
4. Tourist face a lot of problem in exchange the money
5. Increase the work burden of bank employees
6. Totally time consuming process

Positive impact of demonetization

Banks stand to gain meaningfully from implementation of demonetization, but over a period of time. While operating costs could increase in the immediate future, there would be an increase in the low-cost current and savings accounts (CASA), which in turn will rub off favorably on the banks' funding costs and liquidity. This could also have the effect of bringing down deposit and lending rates further without the RBI having to cut its repo rate. A

rise in deposit base will allow banks to lower the blended cost of funds. Rising use of credit/debit cards, net banking and other online payment mechanisms will be another positive, as these would not only lower transaction costs but some of these could help earn some fee income as well.

In the immediate run, we are likely to witness larger bank deposits, price corrections and better tax collection possibilities in the economy—all great for Indian bonds.

Mining will be another sector to benefit from this move as this will hurt illegal/unauthorized mining activities, aiding organized players such as Coal India, NMDC, among others.

1. Reduce the consumption level
2. control over the black money
3. Increase the saving level
4. Reduce NPA
5. Reduce interest rate
6. Increase the employment opportunity by ex bankers
7. Reduce the HAWALA MONEY
8. Reduce round tripping process
9. Increase the liquidity in banks
10. Increase the auditing
11. Denomination currency eliminate black money which casts a long shadow of parallel economy on our real economy' and to curb counterfeit currency, which is used to finance terrorism and drugs and as a conduit for money laundering.
12. Control on fake currency in circulation and terror of financing.
13. Scrapping and replacing these with new one would legally take care of all the black money stored in the form of case

Long Term Impact

In the long run, this is a significant positive shock to the Indian economy and society. If substantially implemented, this will send a strong signal about India's anticorruption drive and is very likely to improve the country's reformist stance.

It also provides a boost to the government's financial inclusion drive, pushing more households towards efficient banking and payment infrastructure. Tax revenues will increase.

Bank deposits will increase and they will have more capacity to support the economy. It will boost growth as it will expand and clean the formal gross domestic product.

Conclusion

The decision of demonetization taken by govt. at initial stage it show a large no of negative impact on maximum sector every where we can see the condition of deflation, and crises. No one have a positive aptitude. But it may possible that this step has a bright future and economy may run on track. According to me if the govt apply this planning with more preparation and management than the problems will reduce The system not follow the right path so circulation of money decrease and many small industrial faces a large scale problems.

References

<http://iasparliament.com>

Archis Mohan (2016) “Demonetization Scrappy Income Tax” Nov15.2017.

Bank Union (2016) “Demonetization of Rs 500 and 1000 has to led Financial chaos “ Nov. 14, 2016

Mohan Y (2016) “How the ban of Rs 1000 and 500 will affect the common man” Nov 24 2016

Pavan kumar , Vijay (2016) “Impact of Demonetization in India “Dec . 12 2016

Shanker (2016) “Demonetization “Nov. 10. 2016